

EFFECT OF ABIOTIC FACTORS ON THE PRODUCTIVITY LINK PARAMETERS OF LAC INSECT, *KERRIA MANIPURENSIS* IN MANIPUR

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ABSTRACT: The study reveals that the initial density of settlement of showed a positive correlation ($r = +0.85$) with morning relative humidity whereas it was negatively correlation with evening humidity ($r = -0.22$), maximum temperature ($r = -0.80$) minimum temperature ($r = -0.77$) and rainfall ($r = -0.33$), respectively. High male percentages 91.63%, 86.54% and 84.77% were observed on all the 4 months crop of existing species of lac insect in Imphal west district under field condition during 2017 to 2019 as against 22.50%, 19.65% and 17.64% on 8 months crop during 2017 to 2020. Correlation analysis showed a positive correlation of sex ratio (male %) with both maximum and minimum temperature, evening humidity and rainfall with r values of 0.86, 0.95, 0.39 and 0.60, respectively indicating high response of weather parameters on the male percentage of lac insect. Fecundity of lac insect showed a positive correlation of $r = +0.62$ indicating great influence of morning relative humidity as against other weather parameters *i.e.* maximum temperature, minimum temperature, evening relative humidity and rainfall which showed negative correlation.

Key words: Lac insect, humidity, temperature, settlement, sex ratio, fecundity

INTRODUCTION

Climate change and extreme weather events affect plants and animals, as a consequence of recent human activities and its effect on global climate, plants and animals face a new environmental condition such as elevated temperature and UV radiation and changes in rainfall patterns and humidity over the seasons. Insect represent almost half of the biodiversity so far described (SPEIGHT *et al.*, 1999) and are central pieces on ecosystem structure and function (CRAWLEY, 1983). Insect are poikilothermic and they change their body temperature according to the external conditions. This is one of the main factors determining their distribution and abundance at any place and at any time. Global climatic changes are expected to impact insect-plant interactions in several ways. They might affect insect directly, through changes in physiology, behaviour and life history parameters, as well as indirectly through changes experienced by host plants in their morphology, physiology and patterns of richness, diversity and abundance. Because of their tight relationship with host plants, insect hervivores are expected to suffer direct and indirect effects of climate change through the changes experienced by their host plants. MADGE and CORNE (1956) reported that survival and abundance of the pest is directly dependent upon its desiccations and rainfall of that area rather than all the influences. The temperature and humidity are undoubtly two major factors which influence most of the activity of insects.

Lac is a valuable gift of nature to mankind. Lac is a resinous exudation from the body of female lac insect (*Kerria manipurensis*), known since Vedic period. It would appear that

Vedic people knew that the lac is obtained from numerous insects. Lac, popularly known as shellac, in its refined flake form, is the resinous substances secreted as a protective covering by a minute lac insect, which is found as a parasite on a number of both wild and cultivated plants. Out of the nine genera and 99 species of lac insects reported throughout the world, 2 genera and 26 species are found in India (SARVADE *et al.*, 2018; SINGH *et al.*, 2020); out of which *Kerria manipurensis* is the most widely available species in the Manipur state. The insect secretes it while feeding on phloem sap of its host plant belongs to Order Hemiptera, Suborder Homoptera, Superfamily Coccoidea, Family Lacciferidae, Genus *Kerria*, species *manipurensis*. The lac insect being parasitic in nature, its survival is also dependant on the health of the plant, which in turn can be affected by climatic vicissitudes. Like any other agricultural crop, lac culture is vulnerable to insect pests and vagaries of weather as it remains permanently attached to host plants from which it derives its nutrition. There has been a significant rise in in the frequency of extreme weather events in recent years affecting the summer lac crop. Most of the weather parameters like temperature, relative humidity, rainfall etc. have much influence on herbivory life either directly or indirectly through influencing host plant vigour. The summer lac crop has been showing unusually high male % during recent years especially during March to July which leads to the crop failures in Manipur condition. Keeping in this view present studies were undertaken to correlate weather factors with productivity link parameters of the existing species of lac insect in Manipur.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study on the correlation of productivity link parameters of lac insect, *Kerria manipurensis* with climatic factor was done at Lamsang Research Field under ICAR-AINP on "Conservation of Lac Insect Genetic Resources", CAU, Imphal. In order to study the correlation of productivity link parameters of lac insect with climatic factors observations were done from 2017 to 2020 in both crop seasons of lac insect *i.e.* 4 months crop (March-July) and 8 months crop (July to March) as per standard procedures. Weather parameters *viz.* temperature (maximum, minimum), relative humidity (morning and evening) and rainfall were collected from ICAR Research Complex for North Eastern Region, Lamphelpat, Imphal for the period from 2017 to 2020 and the average of each of parameters has been calculated for each life cycle. The average weather parameters were correlated with productivity link parameters of lac insect *viz.* initial density of settlement, final density of settlement, mortality percentage, sex ratio (male%) and fecundity (nos/female cell) and the data were analyzed using statistical package SPSS.

Initial density of settlement (number per square cm)

The initial density of settlement were recorded 7 days after the inoculation of brood lac where one square cm area was selected randomly and numbers of lac crawlers settled were counted visually by using magnifying glass at three such sites of the plant *i.e.* lower, middle and upper part of the plant and the average were taken as initial density of settlement.

Initial mortality (%)

The above process was repeated at 21-days after inoculation of broodlac. Under field conditions, process of crawlerss emergence continues upto two weeks. The crawlers, which are not able to find suitable sites for settlement, die due to starvation. Observation at this stage is the true indication of the number of crawlers actually settled and which have started feeding.

$$\text{Initial mortality (\%)} = \frac{\text{Initial density} - \text{Density after 21 days of settlement}}{\text{Initial density}} \times 100$$

Final density of settlement (number/cm²)

Final density of settlement = Initial density – Initial mortality

Sex ratio (male %)

At the time of emergence sex of lac crawlers cannot be distinguished. After a certain period of growth, crawlers can be differentiated into male and female lac insects based on their morphological differences. It was done through visual observation. Males were identified by using magnifying glass lens. The process (as in case of initial density of settlement) was repeated for recording male and female numbers with mean \pm SD values. After counting their numbers, respective percentages of male were calculated.

Fecundity (number of young ones produced by the female insect)

The mature female cells were stored individually into glass vials plugged with cotton for about a month and the emerged and not emerged larvae were counted. The total count is taken as fecundity of the female lac insect.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present studies revealed that the minimum average initial density of settlement per square cm area was recorded in 4 months crop (109.53 crawlers/cm²) during March to July 2019 and maximum was recorded in 8 months crop (130.30 crawlers/cm²) during July 2018 to March 2019 as shown in Table 1. The initial density of settlement of showed a positive correlation ($r = +0.85$) with morning relative humidity where as it was negatively correlate with evening humidity ($r = -0.22$). This reveals that the initial density of settlement of lac insect is greatly influenced by morning relative humidity. The initial density of settlement shows a negative correlation with both the maximum and minimum temperature along with rainfall and r values of $r = -0.80$ in maximum temperature, $r = -0.77$ in minimum temperature, $r = -0.80$ in maximum temperature and $r = -0.33$ in rainfall, respectively. Delayed emergence of scale insect crawlers coincided with unfavorable climatic conditions such as low temperature or very high relative humidity (BEARDSLEY and GONZALEZ, 1975). Earlier experimentation result with scale insect also revealed that very high humidity inhibited crawler activity in *Aulacaspis tegalensis* crawlers (GREATHEAD, 1972).

Similarly final density of settlement of lac insect showed positive correlation of $r = +0.72$ with morning relative humidity while other weather parameters showed negative correlation ranging from $r = -0.63$ in maximum temperature, $r = -0.69$ in case of minimum temperature, $r = -0.38$ in evening R.H and -0.41 in rainfall (Table 2) indicating no impact of weather parameters on final density of settlement except morning relative humidity which showed positive correlation. The present studies also revealed that the maximum mean mortality percentage was 23.10% in 4 months crop during March to July 2019 as against minimum mean mortality percentage of 7.55% was recorded on 8 months crop (July 2019 to March 2020). Correlation analysis showed positive response on all the weather parameters except morning RH which showed negative correlation of $r = -0.54$ as shown in table (3) indicating less mortality percentage with high RH of morning.

Table-1: Correlation of climatic factors with initial density of settlement of existing species of lac insect in Manipur

Season	Months/ year	Initial density of settlement		Temp (°C)		Relative Humidity (%)		Rainfall (mm)	
		Crawlers per sq. cm area	Average	Max. Temp	Min. Temp.	Morning	Evening		
4 months crop	March 2017 to July 2017	U	118.6	116.63	27.34	18.76	87.72	66.52	9.62
		M	110.3						
		L	121.0						
8 months crop	July 2017 to March 2018	U	127.6	130.16	26.43	15.21	91.61	61.35	5.2
		M	127.3						
		L	135.6						
4 months crop	March 2018 to July 2018	U	122.6	123.83	28.42	18.26	87.84	58.76	6.26
		M	124.3						
		L	124.6						
8 months crop	July 2018 to March 2019	U	130.3	130.30	26.77	13.60	88.81	53.04	2.24
		M	129.0						
		L	131.6						
4 months crop	March 2019 to July 2019	U	103.3	109.53	29.26	18.02	85.20	56.04	3.82
		M	110.0						
		L	115.3						
8 months crop	July 2019 to March 2020	U	128.0	125.73	26.58	14.83	90.46	56.06	2.98
		M	122.6						
		L	126.6						
Correlation co-efficient					-0.80	-0.77	0.85	-0.22	-0.33

DAS *et al.* (2019) revealed that the correlation analysis of weather parameters with life cycle duration of lac insect showed a highly significant positive correlation ($r = 0.85^{**}$) with morning relative humidity and significant negative correlation ($r = -0.68^{*}$) with total rainfall. The multiple linear regression analysis showed that total rainfall, maximum temperature, bright sunshine hours, morning and evening relative humidity were the major weather parameters which affected the life cycle duration of *Kerria spp* and these five weather parameters

Table-2: Correlation of climatic factors with final density of settlement of existing species of lac insect in Manipur

Season	Months/ year	Final density of settlement		Temp (°C)		Relative humidity (%)		Rainfall (mm)	
		Crawlers per sq. cm area	Average	Max. Temp	Min. Temp.	Morning	Evening		
4 months crop	March 2017 to July 2017	U	93.6	91.73	27.34	18.76	87.72	66.52	9.62
		M	93.0						
		L	88.6						
8 months crop	July 2017 to March 2018	U	112.3	109.74	26.43	15.21	91.61	61.35	5.2
		M	103.3						
		L	113.6						
4 months crop	March 2018 to July 2018	U	114.0	113.30	28.42	18.26	87.84	58.76	6.26
		M	113.3						
		L	112.6						
8 months crop	July 2018 to March 2019	U	113.3	116.30	26.77	13.60	88.81	53.04	2.24
		M	117.3						
		L	118.3						
4 months crop	March 2019 to July 2019	U	79.0	84.20	29.26	18.02	85.20	56.04	3.82
		M	87.3						
		L	86.3						
8 months crop	July 2019 to March 2020	U	118.3	114.2	26.58	14.83	90.46	56.06	2.98
		M	107.3						
		L	117.0						
Correlation co-efficient					-0.63	-0.69	0.72	-0.38	-0.41

Table -3: Correlation of climatic factors with mortality percentage of lac insect in Manipur

Season	Months/ year	Mortality (%)		Temp (°C)		RH (%)		Rainfall (mm)	
		Per sq. cm area	Average	Max. Temp	Min. Temp.	Morning	Evening		
4 months crop	March 2017 to July 2017	U	21.07	21.17	27.34	18.76	87.72	66.52	9.62
		M	15.68						
		L	26.77						
8 months crop	July 2017 to March 2018	U	11.99	15.58	26.43	15.21	91.61	61.35	5.2
		M	18.85						
		L	16.22						
4 months crop	March 2018 to July 2018	U	7.01	8.49	28.42	18.26	87.84	58.76	6.26
		M	8.85						
		L	9.63						
8 months crop	July 2018 to March 2019	U	13.04	10.73	26.77	13.60	88.81	53.04	2.24
		M	9.07						
		L	10.10						
4 months crop	March 2019 to July 2019	U	23.52	23.10	29.26	18.02	85.20	56.04	3.82
		M	20.63						
		L	25.15						
8 months crop	July 2019 to March 2020	U	7.50	7.55	26.58	14.83	90.46	56.06	2.98
		M	7.58						
		L	7.58						
Correlation co-efficient					0.43	0.54	-0.54	0.45	0.42

Table- 4: Correlation of climatic factors with sex ratio of lac insect found in Manipur

Season	Months/ year	Sex ratio (male %)		Temp (°C)		Relative humidity (%)		Rainfall (mm)	
		Per sq. cm area	Average	Max. Temp	Min. Temp.	Morning	Evening		
4 months crop	March 2017 to July 2017	U	85.27	84.77	27.34	18.76	87.72	66.52	9.62
		M	82.46						
		L	86.58						
8 months crop	July 2017 to March 2018	U	22.87	22.50	26.43	15.21	91.61	61.35	5.2
		M	22.93						
		L	21.71						
4 months crop	March 2018 to July 2018	U	84.94	86.54	28.42	18.26	87.84	58.76	6.26
		M	84.37						
		L	90.31						
8 months crop	July 2018 to March 2019	U	20.55	19.65	26.77	13.60	88.81	53.04	2.24
		M	21.63						
		L	16.78						
4 months crop	March 2019 to July 2019	U	92.95	91.63	29.26	18.02	85.20	56.04	3.82
		M	90.52						
		L	91.42						
8 months crop	July 2019 to March 2020	U	18.74	17.64	26.58	14.83	90.46	56.06	2.98
		M	16.49						
		L	17.71						
Correlation co-efficient					0.86	0.95	-0.83	0.39	0.60

Graph-1: Relation of climatic factors with sex ratio of lac insect found in Manipur

exhibited the highest Adjusted Coefficient of Determination of 86.37% and explained 93.94% of the total variation occurring in the crop growth period. Observation on sex ratio (male%) was also done on both 4 months crop and 8 months crop, & high male percentages were recorded as 91.63%, 86.54% and 84.77% were observed on all the 4 months crop of existing species of lac insect under field condition during 2017 to 2019 as against 22.50%, 19.65% and 17.64% on 8 months crop during 2017 to 2020. Correlation analysis showed a positive correlation with maximum and minimum temperature, evening humidity and rainfall with r values of 0.86, 0.95, 0.39, and 0.60, respectively indicating high response of weather parameters on the male percentage of lac insect. Negative correlation of -0.83 on morning RH has been recorded which showed no impact of morning humidity on male % of lac as shown in Table 4, however comparative studies will be done between the male percent of two season crop correlated with weather parameters for validation.

Finally study on Table-5 reveals that correlation analysis on the fecundity of lac insect showed a positive correlation of $r = +0.62$ indicating great influence of morning RH as against other weather parameters *i.e.* maximum temperature, minimum temperature, evening RH and rainfall which showed negative correlation. High rainfall during the month of July influences lac insect settlement (PATEL *et al.*, 1997). Changes in rainfall patterns, frequent droughts and floods, increased intensity and frequency of cold waves, outbreaks of insect pests and diseases area affecting many biological systems profoundly (IPCC, 2007) and lac sub-sector is also affected equally.

Table-5: Correlation of climatic factors with fecundity of lac insect found in Manipur

Season	Months/ year	Fecundity No. / female cell	Temp (°C)		Relative humidity (%)		Rainfall (mm)
			Max. Temp	Min. Temp.	Morning	Evening	
4 months crop	March 2017 to July 2017	215.6	27.34	18.76	87.72	66.52	9.62
8 months crop	July 2017 to March 2018	226.3	26.43	15.21	91.61	61.35	5.2
4 months crop	March 2018 to July 2018	188.6	28.42	18.26	87.84	58.76	6.26
8 months crop	July 2018 to March 2019	208.6	26.77	13.60	88.81	53.04	2.24
4 months crop	March 2019 to July 2019	202.0	29.26	18.02	85.20	56.04	3.82
8 months crop	July 2019 to March 2020	281.3	26.58	14.83	90.46	56.06	2.98
Correlation coefficient			-0.64	-0.58	0.62	-0.21	-0.41

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